

COMPOSITION OF PRUSSIAN AND TURNBULL'S BLUES. PART VI. MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF THE COMPOUNDS.

BY ABANI K. BHATTACHARYA.

Magnetic susceptibility of various samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues have been determined and the P_{Weiss} values were found to be roughly ranged between 20 and 21 P_{Weiss} magnetons, although their calculated values were 16.5 and 19.6 respectively. The aged samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues gave much closer P_{Weiss} values showing that, on ageing, they become more identical in composition. Slight variations by changing the concentration of the respective reactants have been attributed to the influence of adsorption on the composition of the sols.

Welo and Baudisch (*Nature*, 1925, 116, 606) who have considered the collected data due to Rosenbohm (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1919, 93, 693) and made some new measurements of the susceptibilities of certain complex cyanides and related compounds of iron, suggested that a complex ion, whose effective atomic number equals that of an inert gas, should manifest diamagnetic properties, even though the central atom of the complex possesses a strongly paramagnetic susceptibility value as an individual ion.

The effective atomic number is calculated after Sidgwick on the basis that each co-ordinated unit in the complex is bound to the central atom by electron-sharing bonds. Thus, iron in ferrocyanogen complex, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, with an effective atomic number of 36 is diamagnetic, whereas in ferricyanogen complex with an effective atomic number of 35, it is paramagnetic having a value of $P_{\text{Weiss}} = 10$.

In the determination of the magnetic susceptibility of Prussian and Turnbull's blues in their pure state as ferric ferrocyanide $\text{Fe}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_3$, and ferrous ferricyanide $\text{Fe}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_2$, respectively, the theoretically calculated value would be 116 Weiss magnetons per gram molecular weight, or $116/7 = 16.6$ (approx.) per gram atom of Fe in Prussian blue, and 98 Weiss magnetons per gram molecular weight, or $98/5 = 19.6$ Weiss magnetons per gram atom of Fe in Turnbull's blue.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Prussian and Turnbull's blues were prepared by mixing the respective reactants in equivalent proportion. The samples so prepared were washed free of soluble impurities as far as possible and dried in hot air. A few samples were also dried in the sun. Such samples, as were prepared by

mixing an excess of potassium ferrocyanide, were dialysed till free from the soluble impurities, and the dialysed sol was dried by slow evaporation. In the case of aged samples the reactants were mixed and kept in the mixed condition for several weeks, and then filtered and dried. All the samples were individually estimated for Fe_2O_3 , and the percentage of total Fe present in each was determined.

The magnetic susceptibility of these samples per gram of iron was determined by means of a Curie's balance. Anhydrous cobalt sulphate was used as a standard substance. The magnetic susceptibility was calculated from the formula,

$$P_{\text{weiss}} = 14.04 \sqrt{\chi_m} \cdot \overline{M} \cdot T.$$

where χ_m = susceptibility per gram, and M = mol. wt. [here, M = that weight of the substance which contains one gram atom of Fe]. Knowing that 59.7×10^{-6} = mass susceptibility of anhydrous CoSO_4 , the paramagnetic susceptibility of the substance,

$$P_{\text{weiss}} = 14.07 \sqrt{\chi_m} \overline{M} \cdot T,$$

where M is that weight of the substance which contains one gram atom of Fe and T is the absolute temperature, and $\chi = \frac{59.7 \times 10^{-6} \times \theta}{\phi}$, θ and ϕ being the mass deflections of the substance and anhydrous cobalt sulphate respectively.

TABLE I.

Weiss magneton values of Prussian and Turnbull's blues prepared by mixing the reactants of equal concentrations and in equivalent proportion.

Conc. of the reactants.	P_{weiss} values for blues		Conc. of the reactants.	P_{weiss} values for blues	
	Prussian.	Turnbull		Prussian.	Turnbull,
$M/5$	21.54	21.47	$M/25$	19.84	20.85
$M/10$	20.39	21.28	$M/50$	19.45	21.67
$M/20$	20.89	21.35	$M/100$	19.52	21.47

TABLE II.

P_{weiss} values of the Prussian and Turnbull's blues prepared by ageing the mixture of the reactants along with the precipitate of the blues; the reactants being mixed in equivalent proportion at several concentrations.

Conc. of the reactants.	P_{weiss} values for blues		Conc. of the reactants.	P_{weiss} values for blues	
	Prussian.	Turnbull.		Prussian.	Turnbull.
$M/5$ with $M/5$	20.90	20.93	$M/20$ with $M/5$	20.18	21.60
$M/20$,, $M/20$	21.10	21.38	$M/5$,, $M/40$	20.22	21.08
$M/5$,, $M/20$	20.60	21.10	$M/40$,, $M/5$	19.56	21.71

TABLE III.

P_{Weiss} values of Prussian blues prepared by mixing the reactants at unequal concentrations.

Conc. of the reactants. $\text{FeCl}_3\text{—K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	Proportion of mixing.	P_{Weiss} values.
$M/5$ with $M/2.5$	1 equiv. with 1 equiv.	19.95
$M/10$ " $M/2.5$	" "	19.12
$M/2.5$ " $M/10$	" "	19.57
$M/20$ " $M/2.5$	" "	18.87
$M/3.24$ " $M/2.30$	1 equiv. FeCl_3 with 5/9 equiv. $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	17.55

TABLE IV.

P_{Weiss} values of Turnbull's blues prepared by mixing the reactants at unequal concentrations, proportion of mixing being 1 equiv. : 1 equiv.

Conc. of the reactants. $\text{FeSO}_4\text{—K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	P_{Weiss} values.
$M/5$ with $M/10$	20.58
$M/10$ " $M/5$	20.22
$M/5$ " $M/20$	19.64

DISCUSSION.

From the foregoing tables both Prussian and Turnbull's blues appear to have practically equal Weiss magneton values and the calculated figures from experimental observations approximately range between 20 and 21 Weiss magnetons per gram atom of Fe contained in the substance. From the magnetic additive relations, the Weiss magneton value for $\text{Fe}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_3$ per gram atom of Fe should be 16.5 and that of $\text{Fe}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_2$ should be 19.6. But the experimental values recorded in the above tables show a pretty wide discrepancy, particularly in the case of Prussian blue.

In the light of mutual oxidation and reduction phenomenon that may take place between the reactants, Weiss magneton values of Prussian and Turnbull's blues should be anywhere between 16.5 and 19.6. With the assumption that equal quantities of Prussian and Turnbull's blues are formed, P_{Weiss} values ought to have been the mean of 19.6 and 16.5 or equal to 18.05. The experimental figures are, however, much away, from 18.05, and hence no conclusion can be arrived at regarding the proportion of Prussian and Turnbull's blues formed in the compound.

The aged samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues, however, give much closer P_{Weiss} values, which suggest that by ageing they tend to assume a more similar composition than the fresh ones. This is in support of our

views already advanced on the basis of analytical results (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 213, 242).

P_{weight} values of Prussian and Turnbull's blues are more variable when there is much difference in the concentrations of the mixed reactants e.g., $M/5$ with $M/10$; or $M/10$ with $M/5$. This gives further support to the fact, that the composition of such blues is much influenced by the adsorption phenomenon. The Prussian blue is a better adsorbent for Fe^{+++} and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ than is Turnbull's blue for Fe^{++} and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$; hence, we observe that the P_{weight} values of Prussian blue are farther away from the theoretical value (16.5) than those of the Turnbull's blues. Hence, in Table III the variations of P_{weight} values can only be accounted for by the different degrees of adsorption of the iron, ferro- and ferricyanogen ions, when the blues are precipitated by mixing the respective reactants in unequal concentrations. Thus, when mixed in equivalent proportion, the ferric ion should be adsorbed more than the ferrocyanogen ion, when the ferric chloride is stronger in concentration than potassium ferrocyanide and *vice versa*. Hence, the P_{weight} values of these blues would slightly increase or decrease according to the P_{weight} value of the ion adsorbed.

This view has been practically supported in most cases by the results recorded in Tables III and IV. Magnetic susceptibilities of these compounds, therefore, fairly support the conclusions of the author's analytical results, and the conclusions arrived at from the absorption spectra of their solutions (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 143) in oxalic acid are also in agreement with the magnetic behaviour of the fresh and aged samples of these compounds.

My best thanks are due to Prof. P. Rây of Science College, Calcutta, who kindly allowed me to work in his laboratory with the magnetic balance and to Dr. D. C. Sen, now of Ripon College, Calcutta, who kindly helped me in the use of the apparatus.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
BAREILLY COLLEGE,
BAREILLY.

Received September 26, 1940.